

Peracid Oxidation of Steroidal Oximes

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3 β -Chlorocholest-5-en-7-one oxime (1) and cholest-5-en-7-one oxime (2) on treatment with peracid afford epoxy nitro steroids (3, 4), β -lactone (5), B-nor acid (6) and seco acid (7). The structures of these products have been established on the basis of their analytical and ir, pmr, mass and spectral data.

THE reactions of peracids on steroidal oximes and ketones are known to furnish nitrosteroids¹⁻⁴ and lactones⁵ respectively. In continuation of our earlier report⁴, we now describe the synthesis of epoxy nitrosteroids and β -lactone in quantitative yield from α,β -unsaturated steroidal oximes by using perbenzoic acid as oxidant. The reaction of perbenzoic acid with 3 β -chlorocholest-5-en-7-one oxime (1)⁶ affords 5,6 α -epoxy-7-nitro-5 α -cholest-7-ene (3), 3 β -chloro-B-norcholest-4-en-8 β -ol-6-carboxylic acid-6,8-lactone (5) and 3 β -chloro-B-nor-7 ξ -nitrocholest-4-en-7 ξ -carboxylic acid (6). Under similar reaction conditions, cholest-5-en-7-one oxime (2)⁷ furnished 5,6 α -epoxy-7-nitro-5 α -cholest-7-ene (4) and 5-keto-5,7-seco-6-norcholestan-7-oic acid (7). Structures of the products were supported by their elemental analysis and spectral properties. Probable mechanisms for their formation have been suggested (Schemes 1 and 2).

1; R=Cl
2; R=H
3; R=Cl
4; R=H
5

6

7

Scheme 1

Scheme 2

Experimental

All melting points were determined on Kofler's block apparatus and are uncorrected. Ir spectra (KBr, nujol) were recorded on a Pye-Unicam SP3-100 spectrophotometer, nmr spectra (CDCl_3) on a Varian A-60D instrument using TMS as internal standard, and mass spectra on a JMS D-300/AEI MS-9 spectrometer at 70 eV using direct insertion of technique at a source temperature of about 250°.

Reaction of the oxime (1) with perbenzoic acid: 3 β -Chlorocholest-5-en-7-one oxime (1; 2.5 g, 5.767 mmol) in chloroform (30 ml) was stirred with a solution of perbenzoic acid (25 ml) in chloroform at 0°. After 0.5 h paratoluene sulphonic acid (as a catalyst, few crystals) was added and further stirred for 3 h and worked up in chloroform. The chloroform solution was washed with water, aqueous sodium thiosulphate (5%) and water and

dried (Na_2SO_4). Removal of the solvent under reduced pressure provided an oily residue (2.3 g) which was chromatographed over silica gel (45 g). The column was successively eluted with light petroleum ether-ether (35 : 1.25 : 1 and 20 : 1) to give three fractions respectively. Fraction-I gave 3 β -chloro-5,6 α -epoxy-7-nitro-5 α -cholest-7-ene (3) as an oil which was crystallised from methanol (1.107 g, 2.388 mmol; 42.5%), m.p. 154° (Found: C, 69.7; H, 8.8; N, 3.1. $\text{C}_{27}\text{H}_{42}\text{NO}_2\text{Cl}$ requires: C, 69.97; H, 9.07; N, 3.02%); positive Beilstein test; ν_{max} 1 640 (C=C), 1 560, 1 360 (C-NO₂), 1 250, 1 040 (C-O) and 780 cm^{-1} (C-Cl); δ 3.25 (1H, s, C6- β H), 3.95 (1H, br m, $W_{1/2}$ 20 Hz, C3 α -H), 1.2, 0.91, 0.81 and 0.63 (angular and sidechain methyl protons); M^+ 463/465 ($\text{C}_{27}\text{H}_{42}\text{NO}_2\text{Cl}$), m/z 433/435 (M^+ - NO).

Fraction-II afforded 3 β -chloro-B-norcholest-4-en-8 β -ol-6-carboxylic acid-6,8-lactone as a white solid recrystallised from methanol as needles (0.873 g, 35.0%), m.p. 194° (Found: C, 74.8; H, 9.5. $\text{C}_{27}\text{H}_{41}\text{O}_5\text{Cl}$ requires: C, 75.0; H, 9.94%); positive Beilstein test; ν_{max} 1 810 (C=O, β -lactone)⁵, 1 640 (C=C), 1 050 (C-O), 716 cm^{-1} (C-Cl); δ 5.7 (1H, s, C4-vinyl proton), 3.05 (1H, s, C6 α -H), 3.75 (1H, br m, $W_{1/2}$ 17 Hz, C3 α -H), 1.21, 0.9, 0.7 and 0.66 (CH_3); M^+ 432/434 ($\text{C}_{27}\text{H}_{41}\text{O}_5\text{Cl}$), m/z 397 (M^+ - Cl).

Fraction-III furnished 3 β -chloro-B-nor-7 ξ -nitrocholest-4-en-7 ξ -carboxylic acid (6) as a non-crystallisable semisolid (0.367 g, 13.2%) (Found: C, 67.61; H, 8.7; N, 2.9. $\text{C}_{27}\text{H}_{42}\text{NO}_4\text{Cl}$ requires: C, 67.64; H, 8.76; N, 2.92%); positive Beilstein test; ν_{max} 3 500 (OH), 1 735 (COOH), 1 640 (C=C), 1 575, 1 345 (C-NO₂) and 780 cm^{-1} (C-Cl); δ 6.15 (1H, d, C-4-vinyl proton), 4.2 (1H, br m, $W_{1/2}$ 18 Hz, C3 α -H), 9.8 (1H, br s, COOH, deuterium exchangeable), 1.13, 0.86, 0.76 and 0.6 (CH_3); M^+ 479/481 ($\text{C}_{27}\text{H}_{42}\text{NO}_4\text{Cl}$), m/z 449/451 (M^+ - CO₂).

Reaction of the oxime (2) with perbenzoic acid: Cholest-5-en-7-one oxime (2; 2.5 g, 6.26 mmol) under identical reaction conditions as mentioned earlier and after column chromatography furnished 5,6 α -epoxy-7-nitro-5 α -cholest-7-ene (4) by the elution of petroleum ether-ether (35 : 1) as an oil (1.407 g, 54.1%) (Found: C, 75.4; H, 9.8; N, 3.3. $\text{C}_{27}\text{H}_{42}\text{NO}_2$ requires: C, 75.52; H, 10.02; N, 3.26%); ν_{max} 1 630 (C=C), 1 545, 1 370 (C-NO₂), 1 270 and 1 040 cm^{-1} (C-O); δ 3.45 (1H, s, C6 β -H), 1.25, 0.95, 0.85 and 0.65 (CH_3). Further elution with petroleum ether-ether (10 : 1) afforded 5-keto-5,7-seco-6-norcholestan-7-oic acid (7)⁷, recrystallised from methanol, (0.813 g, 32.6%), m.p. 193° (identical in ir, pmr, m.p. and m.m.p.)⁷.

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